

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

COLLEGE OF ALLIED HEALTH SCIENCES

PROCEEDINGS OF THE MEETING OF BOARD OF STUDIES HELD ON 12.06.2020 AT 9:30 AM IN THE BOARD ROOM

Members present:

1. Dr. Sham Kishore	Chairman,
2. Mr. Naveen Bappanadu	Member
3. Dr. Sukesh	Member
4. Dr. Pavanchand Attavar	Member
5. Dr. Vishrutha K V	Member
6. Ms. Shaik Farheen	Member
7. Ms. Kavya Shettigar K	Member
8. Mrs. Swathi Krishnan	Member
9. Mrs. Swathi D	Member
10. Mr. Devaseelan S	Member
11. Mrs. Laveena D'Souza	Member
12. Dr. Vrinda	Member
13. Ms. Sahana	Member
14. Mrs. Priyadhershini S	Member
15. Mrs. Shwetha B	Member

The BOS discussed the following agenda:

1. Approve the minutes of the last Meeting of the BOS held on 05.03.2020.
2. Change of Topics in the Course of Allied Health Sciences.
3. Conducting Clinical postings and practical sessions amidst Covid Lockdown.
4. Commencement of online Classes.
5. Change of Course name of 'Respiratory Care Technology' to 'Respiratory Therapy'.
6. Proposal for new Chairperson

Agenda No. 1: Confirmations of the minutes of Last Meeting of Board of Studies which was held on 10.03.2020. The Resolution was taken as per the suggestions of the BOS Members in the last meeting, all the Allied Health Sciences Courses were asked to update the changes proposed by the BOS Members.

Agenda No. 2: In the Courses of Allied Health Sciences Few Topics had to be updated and changed. The Resolution was to add the Topic Coronavirus in B.Sc. 3rd Semester (AOT, RT, PFT and Optometry) and the same was added in B.Sc. 4th Semester RDT in the Subject Applied Microbiology (Principal 9) was also been changed.

Agenda No. 3: Conducting Clinical Posting and Practical Sessions – Related: Covid-19 and Lockdown issues. The Resolution was such that as the Covid Norms the Campus had to be

closed for few weeks and hence the students who were needing the Clinical Posting and Practical Sessions and were allowed to be present in the campus with Negative Covid Test report

Agenda No. 4: Due to the restrictions to conduct offline classes in the Campus, in order to fulfil at least the basic knowledge to the students, the faculties are expected to teach through video classes as well as via sharing various video resources to the students. The Resolution was that the Classes were proposed to be conducted online. Meanwhile the number of video classes in a day had to be restricted not exceeding more than 4 hours, considering the network feasibility.

Agenda No. 5: The Discussion regarding the course name change was proposed as in the last meeting regarding the 'Respiratory Care Technology' to 'Respiratory Therapy'. Resolution was taken accordingly; updates and changes were approved as proposed by the BOS.

Agenda No. 6: The proposal for the new chairperson for BOS was discussed. Resolution was taken accordingly, and new BOS chairperson was appointed, the decision was approved as proposed by the BOS.

The meeting was concluded at 11:30 AM with a vote of thanks by Ms. Swathi Krishnan, Member and Board of Studies.

Dr. Sham Kishore,
Chairman,
BOS in Allied Health Science

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Mr. Naveen Bappanadu

Dr. Sukesh

Dr. Pavanchand Attavar

Dr. Vishrutha K V

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